

On the iron ionization balance of cool stars: the role of accurate surface gravities from *Gaia*

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Abstract

High-resolution spectroscopic studies of solar-type stars have revealed higher iron abundances derived from singly ionized species compared to neutral, violating the ionization equilibrium under the assumption of local thermodynamic equilibrium. In this work (Tsantaki *et al.*, 2019), we investigate the overabundances of FeII lines reported in our previous work for a sample of 451 solar-type HARPS stars in the solar neighborhood. The spectroscopic surface gravities which emerge from the ionization balance, appear underestimated for the K-type stars. In order to understand this behavior, we search our FeII line list for unresolved blends and outliers. We use reference parameters (effective temperature and metallicity) and the *Gaia* DR2 parallaxes to derive surface gravities (trigonometric gravities) and calculate the FeI and FeII abundances from different line lists. We exclude the FeII lines which produce overabundances above 0.10 dex. The derived surface gravities from the clean line list are now in agreement with the trigonometric. Moreover, the difference between FeI and FeII abundances is significantly decreased. Finally, we show that the ionization balance of Ti can provide better estimates of surface gravities than iron. With this analysis, we provide a solution to the ionization balance problem observed in the atmospheres of cool dwarfs.

1 Introduction

A standard method to determine the atmospheric parameters via spectroscopy is to measure the equivalent widths (EW) of several neutral and singly ionized iron lines and calculate their abundances. The effective temperature (T_{eff}) and surface gravity ($\log g$) is derived when excitation and ionization balances are satisfied simultaneously under the assumption of local thermodynamic equilibrium (LTE). Even though the above methods provide high enough precision and accuracy for T_{eff} and metallicity, the determination of surface gravity can be problematic (e.g. Mortier *et al.*, 2014) and is difficult to constrain from the ionization balance of iron lines.

Several works in high resolution report discrepancies between neutral and singly ionized iron abundances for dwarf stars in several open clusters (Hyades, Pleiades, and M34) and the Ursa Major moving group (e.g. Yong *et al.*, 2004; Schuler *et al.*, 2010; Aleo *et al.*, 2017). The discrepancies are stronger for the cooler stars ($T_{\text{eff}} < 5200$ K) with systematic higher FeII abundance over FeI. The deviation from the ionization balance is also present in field stars in the solar neighborhood (Allende Prieto *et al.*, 2004; Ramírez *et al.*, 2007). We refer as the *ionization balance problem*, the observed differences between FeI and FeII abundances in LTE.

The ionization imbalance affects directly the determination of surface gravity when it is derived from the FeI–FeII tuning. The comparison of surface gravity from spectroscopy and estimated from more direct methods such as using astrometry (trigonometric $\log g$), shows spurious correlations with T_{eff} with higher deviations for the cooler stars (Tsantaki *et al.*, 2013; Delgado Mena *et al.*, 2017). In the *Gaia* era, we have precise parallaxes for a huge number of stars, and therefore, trigonometric gravities can be used as reference,

assuming well constrained T_{eff} , to test the accuracy of spectroscopic $\log g$.

2 Searching for outliers from HARPS spectra

We use a sample of 451 FGK-type dwarfs to estimate empirically which FeII lines give overabundances for each spectrum. The sample is part of the HARPS ($R \sim 115\,000$) GTO planet search program (Mayor *et al.*, 2003) with very high signal-to-noise ratio. The stellar parameters of this sample were derived by imposing excitation and ionization equilibria on weak iron lines (Sousa *et al.*, 2008; Tsantaki *et al.*, 2013). Their effective temperatures and metallicities are in very good agreement with various spectroscopic and photometric works and thus, we consider these parameters very reliable to be used as reference.

Even though the effective temperatures agree very well with more model-independent methods, surface gravities on the other hand, appear flat in the Hertzsprung–Russell (HR) diagram for the cooler stars (Fig. 1). With the *Gaia* mission (Gaia Collaboration *et al.*, 2018), we have access to parallaxes with unprecedented precision for millions of stars. In lack of other direct $\log g$ estimates, trigonometric gravities are very useful to test our spectroscopic determinations. Trigonometric gravities are derived from the following expression:

$$\log \frac{g}{g_{\odot}} = \log \frac{M}{M_{\odot}} + 4 \log \frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff}_{\odot}}} + 0.4(V + BC) + 2 \log \pi + 0.104 \quad (1)$$

where M is the stellar mass, V the visual magnitude, BC the bolometric correction, and π the parallax in mas. We de-

Figure 1: The HR diagram for the 451 stars for the two set of parameters: the spectroscopic parameters of TS13 (red points), and spectroscopic T_{eff} and $\log g$ from *Gaia* parallaxes (blue points). The dotted and solid lines corresponds to isochrones.

rived the trigonometric $\log g$ from the *Gaia* DR2 parallaxes (Luri *et al.*, 2018), V magnitudes from the Hipparcos catalog (Perryman *et al.*, 1997), bolometric correction based on Torres (2010), solar magnitudes from Bessell *et al.* (1998), and the T_{eff} of TS13. No correction for interstellar reddening is needed since all stars are less than 56 pc. Because of systematics in the *Gaia* DR2 parallaxes, we add a conservative value of 0.03 mas proposed by the *Gaia* collaboration (Lindgren *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, we increase the errors in parallaxes to consider the $\sim 30\%$ underestimation in uncertainties for bright stars (Luri *et al.*, 2018; Arenou *et al.*, 2018). Stellar masses are derived from the PARAM 1.3 tool. The trigonometric $\log g$ are depicted in Fig. 1 which follow the expected isochrones for the solar neighborhood.

In order to evaluate possible overabundances, we perform the following process. First, we measure the EW of the complete TS13 line list for all spectra with ARES (Sousa *et al.*, 2015). Then, we use our reference spectroscopic T_{eff} , $[Fe/H]$, and microturbulence from TS13, and the trigonometric gravities to derive the individual Fe I and Fe II abundances for each star with MOOG (version 2017). The $\log gf$ values of the line list are calibrated to match the solar abundances while the collisional broadening parameters (damping) are based on the Unsold (1955) approximation with an enhancement factor recommended by the Blackwell group. We also consider the damping described by the ABO theory (e.g. Barklem *et al.*, 2000). We evaluate how the two different damping approaches affect the abundances of the Fe II lines.

In Fig. 2, we plot the difference between Fe II – Fe I for the 451 stars using the different damping parameters. In the traditional LTE approach, the differences should be zero but in our case they are enhanced for the cooler stars (~ 0.3 dex) and this is the typical ionization balance problem that is reported in the literature. We notice that there is no distinction from this plot which damping approach performs better as in both

Figure 2: Differences in iron abundances (Fe II – Fe I) as a function of T_{eff} for the 451 stars for the two different damping options. Red points represent the differences with Barklem damping and the blue points the differences with Blackwell. The abundances are derived with the T_{eff} , $[Fe/H]$, and microturbulence from TS13, and the trigonometric $\log g$.

cases the differences in the iron abundances are equally large.

Our goal is to select the Fe II lines which produce the same abundance as Fe I (which is equal to the total iron abundance since it is measured only from Fe I lines). In Fig. 3, we present the differences of the overall iron abundance minus the abundance of each Fe II line for the cooler stars (134 stars) since the Fe II overabundances are more evident for $T_{\text{eff}} < 5200$ K using the two different damping approaches. We exclude lines with median difference higher than 0.10 dex and at the same time their mean absolute deviation is above 3σ .

The remaining good lines for both damping options are: 4508.28, 4620.51, 4656.98, 5234.63, 5264.81, 5414.07, 6247.56 Å. Other reasons for the Fe II overabundances could be related to bad EW measurements because they are in regions difficult to normalize correctly, or their atomic data are not accurate. Summarizing, we exclude 10 out of 18, showing the difficulty to find good Fe II lines in the optical.

2.1 Comparison with other line lists

We perform the same analysis for the line list of Meléndez & Barbuy (2009) which contains 120 Fe II lines order to extend our number of good Fe II lines. We select the lines which fulfill the criteria of Sect. 2 resulting in 15 good lines from Meléndez & Barbuy (2009). Only six lines from Meléndez & Barbuy (2009) are not in the TS13 list and are now included as new good lines.

From the lines in common between TS13 and Meléndez & Barbuy (2009), we select the atomic data of those which present the lowest median and dispersion values. For example, the line 4576.34 Å with the solar calibrated $\log gf$ from TS13 gives difference in the abundances of 0.13 dex, yet with the atomic data of Meléndez & Barbuy (2009) the difference is reduced to 0.07 dex. This test demonstrates that the atomic data play an important role, as important as the correct EW

Figure 3: Difference in abundance ($\text{FeII} - \text{Fe}$) produced by each FeII line for the cool stars of our sample. The dotted lines show the ± 0.10 dex limit. The different colors represent different damping options. The lines in squares are the ones selected by our criteria.

measurement itself, on the abundance analysis. The final line list contains 14 lines from both Meléndez & Barbuy (2009) and TS13 and is presented in Tsantaki *et al.* (2019).

3 Ionization balance of iron for the 451 HARPS stars

Now, we perform the inverse exercise to show that in fact the clean FeII list we compiled provides more reliable surface gravities. We derive the atmospheric parameters for the sample using the spectral analysis tool FASMA¹ (Andreasen *et al.*, 2017; Tsantaki *et al.*, 2018). The mean differences and standard deviations between the $\log g$ of this work and the trigonometric is 0.02 and 0.10 dex, and between the $\log g$ of TS13 and trigonometric is -0.06 and 0.13 dex. There is a clear improvement in the $\Delta \log g - T_{\text{eff}}$ relation in this work and our dispersion values are smaller. These results indicate that the criteria of the line selection were efficient enough.

Using the spectroscopic T_{eff} and $[Fe/H]$, and the trigonometric gravity, we calculate the new FeII and Fe abundances for our sample similarly as in Sect. 2. In Fig. 4, we plot the difference in $\text{FeII} - \text{Fe}$ with T_{eff} for the whole sample of 451 stars. This plot shows that ionization balance is on average fulfilled for the lines we consider clean after the blending

¹FASMA tool: <http://www.iastr.pt/fasma>

Figure 4: Difference between $\text{FeII} - \text{Fe}$ abundances for the stars of our sample with the clean FeII list with T_{eff} .

analysis. The $\text{FeII} - \text{Fe}$ mean difference is -0.01 dex and the standard deviation is 0.04 dex, and thus, we can say that the ionization balance is much better satisfied. The highest dispersion appears for the cooler stars. The remaining differences can be attributed to the effects we did not consider in this work, e.g. model uncertainties related to granulation and activity of K-type stars (Ramirez, 2008) but to be fully understood, 3D non-LTE investigations should be carried out.

4 Ionization balance of titanium for the 451 HARPS stars

Apart from iron, other species could be more suitable for the surface gravity determinations. The element with most numerous ionized lines in the line list Neves *et al.* (2009) after iron is Ti and contains 30 TiI and 8 TiII lines. We modify FASMA to obtain surface gravities from the ionization equilibrium of Ti, having the other stellar parameters fixed to the values of TS13. The mean difference and standard deviation between $\log g$ derived from Ti and the trigonometric is 0.00 and 0.09 dex and are smaller than the derived from the Fe ionization equilibrium (Fig. 5).

The Ti line list in this Section gives smaller standard deviations than Fe and flattest slopes with T_{eff} . Therefore, Ti is a better indicator to probe surface gravity than Fe, once the other stellar parameters are defined.

5 Conclusions

The ionization balance problem has troubled astronomers in several works in the literature. Several hypotheses have been proposed to explain the differences between FeII and Fe abundances but with no fully satisfactory answer yet. In this work (Tsantaki *et al.*, 2019), we propose line blending as the main reason for the overabundances of FeII . We investigate the quality of our FeII line list for unresolved blends that were missed by visual inspection from previous work.

We perform an empirical test to remove FeII lines using high resolution spectra of 451 solar-type stars with reference

Figure 5: Differences in $\log g$ of the TS13 (red points) with the trigonometric and from Ti of this work with the line list of Neves et al. (2009) (green points) with the trigonometric as a function T_{eff} . The colored lines in the bottom plot represent the linear fits of the two samples.

stellar parameters (T_{eff} , $[Fe/H]$, and microturbulence) from our previous work. Additionally, we combined the iron line list from Meléndez & Barbuy (2009) to enhance the number of lines or improve the atomic data of the existing. More accurate gravities are derived based on the *Gaia* parallaxes in conjunction with precise spectroscopic effective temperatures. Using these parameters, we exclude the FeII lines which give abundances higher than 0.10 dex and dispersion lower than 3σ . The clean FeII line list contains 14 lines.

Finally, we show that the ionization equilibrium of Ti provides more accurate surface gravities than iron using for the Ti line list of Neves et al. (2009). Even though surface gravity still remains the parameter most difficult to constrain via spectroscopy, there are significant improvements presented in this work and in lack of parallax measurements, we can now provide more accurate surface gravities even for the lower main sequence stars.

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